

ECOLOGICAL AND ECONOMIC ASPECTS OF
REPRESENTATIVES OF THE CHENOPODIACEAE
SUBFAMILY IN THE CONDITIONS OF
KARAKALPAKSTAN

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ABSTRACT

The Republic of Karakalpakstan occupies about 40% of Uzbekistan's territory and is located in the northwest of the country. The region's climate is sharply continental and arid, with annual precipitation of 100-150 mm, occurring mainly during the winter-spring period [1].

Introduction. The Republic of Karakalpakstan occupies about 40% of Uzbekistan's territory and is located in the northwest of the country. The region's climate is sharply continental and arid, with annual precipitation of 100-150 mm, occurring mainly during the winter-spring period [1]. The primary water source is the Amu Darya River; however, in recent decades, its water availability has notably decreased. The ecological crisis caused by the shrinking of the Aral Sea has led to land degradation and increased soil salinization, which has affected the region's flora and contributed to the spread of xerophytic and halophytic plants, particularly representatives of the Chenopodiaceae subfamily [2, 4].

The aim of this work is to study the representatives of the Chenopodiaceae subfamily in Karakalpakstan and to assess their ecological and biological characteristics as well as their economic significance.

Research objectives: to determine the distribution of the main Chenopodiaceae species in the region and analyze their adaptation to arid and saline soils, as well as to identify promising species for use in agriculture and restoration of degraded lands.

Research methods. Field observations, herbarium specimens and literature sources were used, along with analysis of the ecological and floristic composition of plant communities in the desert zones of Karakalpakstan (Kyzylkum, Ustyurt) [1,3].

Results and discussion. The flora of the region includes over 1100 plant species, a significant portion of which are halophytes [3]. Among Chenopodiaceae, the most widespread are saxaul, keyreuk, cherkez, teresken, izen, and other species [2,4]. They form the primary plant communities in deserts and are valuable fodder crops, especially for Karakul sheep.

Species of the Chenopodiaceae subfamily exhibit high resistance to abiotic stresses (drought and salinity) and contain proteins and biologically active substances with

antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, and antimicrobial properties [4,5]. For instance, the protein content in izen is comparable to that of alfalfa, making it an important fodder resource in desert zones.

In recent years, large-scale work has been carried out in Karakalpakstan to cultivate some Chenopodiaceae species in degraded and saline lands to create artificial pastures and expand fodder lands. Special attention is paid to saxaul, cherkez, and keyreuk to restore vegetation cover and increase pasture productivity [5].

Conclusions. Representatives of the Chenopodiaceae subfamily play a key role in the desert ecosystems of Karakalpakstan. Their study has fundamental significance (in systematics, ecology, and physiology) and practical value for agriculture, land reclamation, and animal husbandry. Further research on this subfamily in the Aral Sea region is relevant for developing sustainable agricultural systems and breeding drought-resistant crops in the region.

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